

Latency-Aware Kubernetes Scheduling for Microservices Orchestration at the Edge

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Abstract—Network and computing infrastructures are nowadays challenged to meet the increasingly stringent requirements of novel applications. One of the most critical aspect is optimizing the latency perceived by the end-user accessing the services. New network architectures offer a natural framework for the efficient orchestration of *microservices*. However, how to incorporate accurate latency metrics into orchestration decisions still represents an open challenge.

In this work we propose a novel architectural approach to perform scheduling operations in Kubernetes environment. Existing approaches proposed the collection of network metrics, e.g. latency between nodes in the cluster, via purposely-built external measurement services deployed in the cluster. Compared to other approaches the proposed one: (i) collects performance metrics at the application layer instead of network layer; (ii) relies on latency measurements performed inside the service of interest instead of utilizing external measurement services; (iii) takes scheduling decisions based on effective end-user perceived latency instead of considering the latency between cluster nodes.

We show the effectiveness of our approach by adopting an iterative discovery strategy able to dynamically determine which node operates with the lowest latency for the Kubernetes pod placement.

Index Terms—Edge, Orchestration, Kubernetes, Latency, Service Placement

I. INTRODUCTION

Next generation services pose novel challenges in the management and orchestration of network and computing infrastructures. Envisioned requirements in terms of latency, bandwidth, and reliability can only be met with a tight coupling between digital infrastructures and the services they host. Such integration is achievable by introducing more flexibility at both the network and computing layers. While at the network layer the required flexibility has been introduced by novel paradigms such as software defined networking and network function virtualization, the computing layer sees the emergence of *microservices*, *cloud-native* and *edge computing* paradigms as a means to meet requirements of the next generation applications.

To fully benefit from distributed computing infrastructures provided by edge computing, software architectures must be designed accordingly. A fundamental software architecture pillar for the so-called *edge-native* applications is represented by microservices. Microservices are a software architectural approach that consists in decomposing applications into small, stateless, independently developed and deployed services able

Fig. 1. Our vision to optimize E2E latency.

to communicate among each other, following the Service Based Architecture model.

Microservices are usually deployed into containers and need orchestration frameworks to handle their lifecycles [1]. Kubernetes [2] has emerged as a reference platform for the orchestration of containers. It allows to automate, manage, and schedule the deployment of microservices in the form of one or more containers wrapped into entities called pods, which represent the smallest deployable units in Kubernetes. Pods can be deployed in *clusters* and can be scheduled over physical machines in different locations which are referred to as *nodes*.

A key component for the orchestration of microservices in Kubernetes is the scheduler which is responsible to elaborate and perform the placement of pods over the nodes. Being devised for traditional cloud environments relying on centralized high-capacity datacenters, standard Kubernetes scheduling strategies are aimed at optimizing computation resources such as CPU and memory [3]. However, considering edge scenarios, scheduling decisions may significantly impact the performance achievable by the applications orchestrated via Kubernetes.

Orchestration driven by application requirements still represents an open challenge in Kubernetes environment and some research efforts have been made in this direction. To

achieve this goal, architectural solutions enabling network-awareness in scheduling decisions need to be investigated. In [4] a scheduling strategy is proposed based on static characterization of network latency between cluster nodes. [5] proposes a heuristic strategy for the deployment of placeholder pods for enhanced reliability and takes into account inter-node latency. [6], [7] propose Kubernetes scheduler extensions to introduce network-awareness for efficient placement of pods. The above mentioned approaches focus on network awareness and rely on latency metrics collected at the network layer via independent applications responsible to monitor network performance parameters to optimize inter-container latency. However, latency experienced by end-users includes network latency to reach the cluster and a non-negligible contribution of the application-layer which for example may be impacted by computational resource saturation, hardware heterogeneity through cluster nodes and other external conditions. The problem of optimizing End-to-End (E2E) latency is not directly addressed in literature and can be solved reporting to the scheduler the measured E2E latency.

In this work, we propose an architectural solution to perform scheduling decision taking into account accurate E2E latency data collected at the application-layer by the orchestrated service. We show the effectiveness of our architectural approach by implementing a discovery strategy able to dynamically allocate pods over the best physical nodes via ad-hoc deployment of replicas of the services. The proposed approach is able to reduce the latency experienced by users while at the same time maintains a low resource usage which represents a critical aspect in terms of costs [8]. The proposed approach differs from the current state of the art since, up to our knowledge, is the first work that addresses the E2E latency awareness instead of the inter-services latency, as graphically illustrated in Fig. 1. Compared to other approaches, the proposed one takes scheduling decision basing on latency metrics collected at the application layer instead of the network one. Further novelty of our solution is represented by the fact that it considers performance experienced by the orchestrated service instead of relying on an external measurement service. Thus, it allows to take more accurate and effective scheduling decisions able to adapt to dynamic conditions, e.g., user mobility and traffic and computational conditions fluctuations.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model refers to a physical infrastructure consisting of a Kubernetes cluster where a set of $N = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k\}$ nodes is managed by a Control Plane, as shown in the principle diagram in Fig. 2.

The objective of the proposed method is to instantiate the service in the node closest to the end-user in terms of latency. This is reached by means of a *sentinel* replica of our service that enables the measurement of end-to-end application-layer latency for every node of the cluster. The enabling mechanism is a custom scheduler in the control plane that instantiates the service in multiple nodes, keeping track of which service is instantiated in which node. The symmetric functionality is the

Fig. 2. System Architecture.

de-scheduler in the control plane which retrieves the latency information and deletes the less performing service instances. Both the user and the nodes run the *latency-meter* application which is instantiated as the client at the user side and as the server in the Kubernetes cluster. The server side of the *latency-meter* application is deployed through the custom scheduler in the Kubernetes cluster. The communication between the application and the de-scheduler is provided by the MQTT protocol via an MQTT broker.

The details and the functional description of the aforementioned components is reported in the following subsections.

A. Scheduler

Normally, the selection of which node will host a pod is often driven by the default Kubernetes scheduler. Its primary target is to optimize resource allocation in the cluster trying to fit the highest possible number of services inside the infrastructure. This selection, when not enforced, is opaque to both developers and clients of the target server application: from their point of view, the selected node is *random* and unpredictable. The expected latency is something in between the best and the worst case among all the cluster nodes. The use of a prediction mechanism is obviously possible but it would cause a significant overhead on the control plane as the number of applications and nodes increases. Furthermore, the prediction of the best choice in terms of network latency for the users requires a huge amounts of measurements data that may not be collected during the whole pod's lifecycle. In our model, instead, we adopt an *iterative* discovery strategy able to meet the optimal pod allocation in terms of the latency experienced by the clients of a target application. Our strategy generates a low overhead and does not rely on a predictor. It

is worth noting that this approach also solves the cold-start problem when the available historical data are not sufficient for the system to take decisions.

This process is realized by providing custom latency aware scheduling and a de-scheduling services. Those two services cooperate together to iteratively move the service to the node which is nearest to the end-user. At each step, only the replica of the service with the best latency survives to the selection made from the de-scheduler. Then, the scheduler instantiates a new replica on a node which has not been tested yet. To do this, the scheduler keeps track of:

- N : the set of all the nodes in the cluster;
- V : the set of visited nodes in the cluster;
- U : the set of nodes to be probed which is $U = N - V$.

While running the latency aware scheduling mechanism it is possible to distinguish two main phases. The first one is a transient phase in which a sentinel replica of the Pod is deployed on each node to probe the application-layer latency. The second one starts when all nodes have been measured by the sentinel replica and the final decision happened. The latency goes down to the minimum allowed by current environmental conditions and remains stable for the end user in stationary conditions. The process is completely transparent to the end-user with no downtime during the whole process. The end-user will experiment only a variation in latency that converges to the minimum available in the cluster, i.e. an improvement in performances.

After a configured timeout, the V set is emptied, so that the iteration can start again to detect and select the current best node allocation for the application. This enables the system to adapt to either a user that changes its position in relation to the cluster's nodes or a temporary change in network or computation available conditions that degrades the latency to a specific node.

The scheduler logic works as follows. Upon the request for scheduling a pod, the scheduler deploys an additional sentinel replica to test latency from another node. The procedure follows the steps shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Scheduling logic

- Input:** Application App
Input: Set of nodes in the cluster N
Input: Set of visited nodes V
Input: Set of untested nodes U
Output: The selected node $n_i \in N$

```

1:  $U \leftarrow N - V$ 
2: while  $U \neq \{\}$  do
3:    $n_i \leftarrow random(U)$ 
4:    $V \leftarrow V \cup \{n_i\}$ 
5:    $scheduleProbe(n_i)$ 
6:    $U \leftarrow N - V$ 
7: end while

```

The scheduling algorithm then waits for the de-schedule to kill one pod. The killed pod will be re-introduced to the

Fig. 3. Latency Measurements data structure used to store latency information.

scheduling queue from the Kubernetes controller and so the schedule can move forward scanning remaining nodes. When all the nodes have been visited, pod placement will be optimal in terms of latency. The sentinel replica used as probe by the scheduler is no longer needed and will not be scheduled again. Instead, if U is not empty, the node n_i is selected according to external requirements (e.g., load balancing, available resources etc.) or randomly.

B. Latency Measurement

The latency measurement application is composed by a client and a server application and has the aim to measure latency to the responding pod. This behaviour can be easily reproduced inside a real world application with little or no effort. In particular, the client has to measure, average and provide the current round-trip time (RTT) to reach the pod hosting the application server and the one hosting the sentinel replica, both accessible through the same IP address through a Kubernetes NodePort Service. This information is then sent to the de-scheduler (detailed in subsection II-C) to decide which is the less-performing replica of the application in the cluster.

MQTT [9] protocol and a MQTT Broker have been adopted for this purpose to decouple the communication: a configured MQTT topic (e.g., latency-measurement) is used to exchange latency information. On one side, once the application client has measured and averaged the current RTT , it *publishes* such information, along with the ID of the measured node and a time reference, on the MQTT topic. On the other side, every component which requires the latency information (i.e., the de-scheduler) can *subscribe* to the MQTT topic to obtain and store such information.

The RTT measurements are stored in a global data structure called *LatencyMeasurements (LM)* which is shown in Fig. 3. This structure keeps the RTT information on a per-application basis: the entry for an application contains the list of the pods of such application along with the list of received measurements data. Every measurement contains the node from where the pod run, the actual measurement and a timestamp counter used to relate the measurement with the time of measurement.

Fig. 4. De-scheduling flow

C. De-Scheduler

The de-scheduler component is responsible for retrieving the measurement from the MQTT broker and deleting the worst performing pods. Its operation are described in Fig. 4:

- 1) Once activated, the de-scheduler contacts the MQTT Broker to *subscribe* to the MQTT topic that receives the RTT measurements
- 2) When an application client communicates with the server, it measures the RTT to communicate to a specific pod
- 3) After a Time of Observation, the measured RTTs are averaged and serialized
- 4) The average RTT along the pod ID and timestamp are *published* to the MQTT topic via the MQTT Broker
- 5) Since the de-scheduler is subscribed to the MQTT topic, it receives the RTT data. It de-serializes the data and creates a new entry in the *LM* data structure, invoking the de-scheduling logic to decide if and which pod has to be de-scheduled.

The de-scheduling logic is triggered when there are enough measurements stored in the *LM* structure for a give application. In particular, we define the *De-scheduling Threshold* T as the minimum number of measured pods required to trigger the de-scheduling logic. For example, $T = 2$ means that the de-scheduler is triggered when it receives the RTT measurement from at least 2 different pods. In general, given R_n as the number of desired replicas for the service, then we have $T = R_n + 1$.

The de-scheduling logic works as follows (Algorithm II-C). The de-scheduler monitors the number of measured pods M in the *LM* data structure of the target application *App*. Once such number is greater or equal to the configured De-scheduling threshold T , the pod p_k with the worst RTT is retrieved, de-scheduled and its measurements are deleted from *LM*. If two pods have the same RTT, the one with the older measurement timestamps is removed.

The de-scheduling of a pod will cause a mismatch between current state and desired one inside the Kubernetes cluster. The Kubernetes controller tries to bring back the system to the desired state adding a new pod to the scheduling queue. This

triggers the scheduler which starts a new scheduling procedure for the pod. As mentioned in Section II-A, the latency aware scheduler stores the set of visited nodes, i.e. the nodes that have or had a pod running for target application. This set of nodes is excluded from the set of new schedulable nodes taken into account by the scheduling procedure. Eventually, the set of visited nodes will be equal to the available nodes, causing the scheduler and the de-scheduler mechanism to stop. This is an intended behaviour and leaves the application running on the $T - 1$ best performing nodes, according to the desired state declared by the application server itself.

III. IMPLEMENTATION & RESULTS

The presented approach has been implemented in a cluster of 10 virtual nodes. Nodes are Virtual Machines running on a micro-datacenter on VMware ESXi hypervisor controlled by a VMware vCenter platform. Each VM runs a MicroK8s Kubernetes distribution on the top of the latest Ubuntu 22.04.1 LTS operating system. We configured the cluster with high-availability capabilities, enabling the master node capabilities on each VM. This provides by default control-plane resiliency and high availability over node failure in addition to the application-layer high availability provided by Kubernetes. We deployed CoreDNS on Kubernetes to provide Domain Name resolution inside the cluster and ease the communications through our deployed applications.

Latency in this scenario depends by network and application latency. In a real deployment of the infrastructure, it is reasonable to assert the application-layer latency is slightly lower than the network one for nearly-real-time and low latency applications. This means that the network distance from the client to the server gives the most of the latency contribution. In our specific implementation, all VMs were co-located and had the same network latency to the client. To overcome that, we randomize the latency of each node around an arbitrary mean value per node with a given variance [10]. The mean values for each of the 10 nodes are respectively 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 100, 200, 350 ms.

Algorithm 2 De-scheduling logic (simplified)

Input: Application *App*
Input: De-Scheduling Threshold T
Input: Latency Measurements *LM*

```

1: while True do
2:    $M \leftarrow$  number of measured pods for App
3:   if  $M \geq T$  then
4:     /* Retrieve the pod with maximum RTT */
5:      $p_k \leftarrow \max_{RTT}(LM, App)$ 
6:     /* Deschedule  $p_k$  and clear its entry in LM */
7:     Deschedule( $p_k$ )
8:      $LM[App][p_k] \leftarrow None$ 
9:   end if
10: end while
  
```

```

Initializing the descheduler... |
Starting MQTT client... |
[mqtt] Subscribing to latency-meter... |
Watching for latency information... |
[mqtt] Received a message: b'{"node": "ip-172-31-19-180", "pod": "
lm-server lm-server-6c4bb484cb-b79vz 29944 |
[mqtt] Measurement added for lm-server-6c4bb484cb-b79vz on node ip
Only one pod measured. Not all measured. Returning false |
[mqtt] Received a message: b'{"node": "ip-172-31-16-225", "pod": "
lm-server lm-server-6c4bb484cb-b79vz 29944 |
lm-server lm-server-6c4bb484cb-pnspb 392263 |
[mqtt] Measurement added for lm-server-6c4bb484cb-pnspb on node ip
[mqtt] All measurement retrieved for lm-server |
lm-server-6c4bb484cb-pnspb (namespace latencyawareapp) killed |

```

```

ts, #node, nodename, #measurements, RTT, Time interval (seconds)
1674931630104318, 9, ip-172-31-28-128, 9, 224446.88888888888, 2.050596
1674931632607386, 6, ip-172-31-22-125, 32, 62324.21875, 2.041185
1674931634880344, 9, ip-172-31-28-128, 9, 231989.77777777778, 2.149329
1674931637395034, 6, ip-172-31-22-125, 34, 58127.705882352944, 2.00983
1674931639516348, 7, ip-172-31-28-134, 29, 68080.1724137931, 2.005692
1674931641691738, 6, ip-172-31-22-125, 32, 62283.625, 2.037955
1674931643810104, 6, ip-172-31-22-125, 32, 61373.9375, 2.001882

```

Fig. 5. Excerpt of the output measurements taken from our Latency Aware de-scheduler (top side) and from our Latency Measurement Client app (bottom side)

Fig. 6. Mean Round Trip Time measured over time from the client perspective

To implement the behaviour described in previous sections, we designed and developed a set of micro-services [11] which implement all the described logic.

After running the application into the Kubernetes cluster, the Latency Measurement Client (LMC) application needs to be configured to point to the cluster. When the client starts, it begin to collect latency metrics of the application latency. The server replies to the client requests providing information about the pod which is handling the task. Once messages are received by the client, the LMC application is able to measure the overall RTT which is composed by two contributes: the network’s latency and the application’s latency. This value is sent to the MQTT Broker topic along with the ID of the measured pod. The de-scheduler gets the metrics from the MQTT Broker topic. When it has got enough metrics to do a comparison, it decides which is the pod that is performing

worse and kills it applying the algorithm in Sec. II-C. At this point, the Kubernetes controller discovers that the current status does not match with the desired state and asks for the creation of a new pod. Our schedule takes in charge the request and processes the creation of the new pod and the scheduling on one of the remaining nodes, following the algorithm 1. The LMC application, meanwhile, continues to measure the latency and is not aware on what is going on inside the cluster. The client perceives only a latency fluctuation due to the service migrating to the end user.

Fig. 5 shows the output of the de-scheduler application (top-side) and the one of the LMC (bottom-side). The red square on the de-scheduler output highlights the moment in which the de-scheduler kills the latency meter server (e.g. lm-server). The red square on the client’s output shows the change in latency measured by the client.

The default scheduler is only able to schedule the required pod once. This means that the placement is done only at scheduling time and the server-side application deployed is bounded to a specified node’s latency. In our case, we assume that the chosen node is the one with 200ms of latency. This is the starting point of both *latency aware* and default scheduler curves in Fig. 6. We use the default Kubernetes scheduler as a baseline, in the case where both the default scheduler and our latency aware scheduler chose the same node at the beginning. The default scheduler does not take any further decision so the latency only fluctuate following Gaussian distribution around the average measured latency until the network is not congested. On the other hand, our latency aware scheduling mechanism can decrease end-to-end latency step by step while probing all the cluster nodes by means of the sentinel replica.

Fig. 6 shows that our proposed latency-aware scheduler significantly reduces the latency while probing new nodes. For each new node evaluated, the perceived latency is bi-stable between the current minimum latency discovered and the latency the node to which the sentinel replica is deployed at the moment. The best fit curve is an interpolation that describes the attended mean latency value at each time using our approach. At second 120 in Fig. 6 all nodes in the cluster have been probed by the sentinel. The de-scheduler takes its final decision saving the lowest latency’s pod. From second 120 onward, the measured value is around 1ms, which is the lowest end-to-end application-layer latency allowed in our setup. This means that our mechanism converged to the best solution and no other action is required.

A. Convergence time

A relevant performance evaluation parameter is represented by the *convergence time*, that is the time interval needed to converge on the scheduling decision able to minimize the E2E experienced latency at application layer. This time, in general, depends on many environmental variables. As shown in Eq.1, we model the convergence time T_C as:

$$T_C = (1 + P_L) \times N \times (T_O + T_S + T_D + T_{COM}), \quad (1)$$

where:

- P_L is the probability to be forwarded to an already analyzed service and the need to repeat measurement;
- N is the number of nodes in the Kubernetes cluster;
- T_O is the Time of Observation needed to measure consistently the latency over one responding service;
- T_S is the Scheduling Time, needed by our Latency Aware Scheduler to schedule the pod through the Kubernetes REST API;
- T_D is the De-Scheduling Time, needed by our De-Scheduler to kill and remove the selected pod through the Kubernetes REST API;
- T_{COM} is the Time of Communication needed to send messages through the MQTT Broker to the de-scheduler.

We empirically evaluate the average time required by Kubernetes APIs to perform scheduling and de-scheduling operations. Basing on our empirical evaluations, we assume $T_S = 3s$ and $T_D = 3s$. Being the communication time T_{COM} in the scale of milliseconds, we consider the impact of T_{COM} negligible.

Since T_S and T_D values are constant and depends on the Kubernetes cluster, we evaluate the convergence time by varying the two remaining degrees of freedom, i.e., T_O and N , as shown in Fig. 7. The convergence time T_C grows following a linear trend with T_O . T_O is a configurable parameter in our system and its variation may lead on excessive overhead or to not update decisions. The selection of the best T_O value is out of the scope of this paper and will be discussed in future works. Although the growth of N can lead to very high T_C for huge clusters it is worth mentioning that, no matter what value of T_O or N in the system, the proposed approach converges in finite time with no service disruption during the whole process.

The proposed approach represents a suitable basis for effective scheduling decisions based on experienced end-to-end latency. Having shown the feasibility of such approach, future directions include the development of more complex scheduling strategies able to realize continuous and event-triggered monitoring of performance to avoid sounding of latency over all the N edge nodes in the network and consequently reduce the convergence time.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this work we propose a novel architectural approach to perform scheduling operations in Kubernetes environment, taking into account user-perceived latency measured at the application layer of the service of interest. The proposed approach addresses current gaps of existing Kubernetes schedulers which traditionally focus on network layer measurement collected among cluster nodes via external services.

Starting from the proposed approach, we implement a latency-aware scheduling mechanism which explores nodes in the cluster by placing ad-hoc replica of the services to finally place the pod on the node able to offer lowest latency to the end-user. This guarantees service continuity while reducing the latency.

Fig. 7. The convergence time needed by the proposed approach in relation to T_O and the Number of Nodes.

Results show that our approach allows to outperform the default Kubernetes scheduler in terms of end-user experienced latency. Future directions include the extension of this work to scenarios with user mobility and the development of optimized scheduling strategies able to reducing the convergence time required for the pod placement.

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